

IN-SITU FULL-FIELD STRAIN MAPPING BY HIGH RESOLUTION EBSD AND J-INTEGRAL ANALYSIS OF A SHORT FATIGUE CRACK IN SINGLE-CRYSTAL NICKEL

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The total fatigue life of structural materials can be predominantly determined by the propagation of short fatigue cracks. Their behaviour is difficult to predict as these cracks grow within a changing local crystallographic environment and interact with features in the microstructure such as grain boundaries. In this study, the stress fields acting locally on a fatigue crack have been observed and characterised in situ for the first time. High-resolution electron backscatter diffraction (HR-EBSD) was used for full-field observations of the local strain fields at a short fatigue crack tip. The crack was initiated on the (111) plane using flexural ultrasonic loading of a single-crystal (001) nickel foil specimen, with maximum stress parallel to [100]. The crack was then loaded in a pre-tilted tensile stage for in situ HR-EBSD. The elastic strain fields were mapped and integrated into their equivalent displacement fields. Finite element post-processing of these displacements provided the mixed-mode stress intensity factors, which quantified their evolution with increasing load.

Keywords: Short fatigue crack, HR-EBSD, Stress intensity factor, In situ strain mapping

INTRODUCTION

Understanding of the behaviour of short fatigue cracks is necessary to improve the durability and reliability of structural materials. Short cracks exhibit significant fluctuations in their growth rates (Suresh and Ritchie[1], Navarro and Delosrios[2], Wan and Dunne[3]), making it difficult to predict their fatigue life accurately using models that are typically fitted to data obtained in the long crack regime. The study of short fatigue cracks is of great importance, as they can constitute a substantial portion of the overall fatigue life of an engineering component. This intricacy in their behaviour is primarily due to microstructural sensitivity. Short fatigue cracks grow within a changing crystallographic environment and can interact with microstructural features along their path (King, et al.[4], Marrow, et al.[5], Wilkinson[6], Dunne, et al.[7], Zhai, et al.[8], Ludwig, et al.[9], Bennett and McDowell[10]), such as grain boundaries. To gain insights into the processes occurring at the crack tip, and to better inform predictive models, local measurements are necessary to characterise the deformation fields that govern the crack propagation mechanism.

The nature of scanning electron microscopy (SEM) facilitates in situ full-field observation of short fatigue cracks with high spatial resolution. The electron backscatter diffraction (EBSD) technique

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utilises the Kikuchi patterns generated by backscattered electrons to obtain information on the state of crystalline materials, including crystal orientation (Adams, et al.[11]), phase (Dingley[12]), elastic strain (Wilkinson, et al.[13], Kacher, et al.[14], Wilkinson, et al.[15], Wilkinson, et al.[16]), and stored dislocations ([16], Britton, et al.[17], He, et al.[18]). In particular, the high-resolution EBSD (HR-EBSD) framework developed by Britton and Wilkinson can achieve elastic strain mapping at an accuracy of $\sim 1 \times 10^{-4}$ (Britton and Wilkinson[19]). Diffraction techniques, such as EBSD and HR-EBSD can therefore extract information on both the plastic and elastic deformations in the crack tip region, and connect the advance of the crack to crystallographic features at the microscale.

Originating from the JMAN method (Becker, et al.[20], Becker, et al.[21]), finite element (FE) post-processing can be used to parameterise the crack strain field by evaluating the J -integral directly from experimental observations of full field displacement data ([21], Koko, et al.[22], Barhli, et al.[23]). Mixed-mode stress intensity factors (Parks[24], Shih and Asaro[25]) can also be extracted. In our previous work, 2D displacement fields obtained by digital image correlation were used, with linear elastic assumptions, to characterise the crack tip condition of a short crystallographic fatigue crack in a zirconium alloy, observed in situ, in terms of local mixed-mode stress intensity factors (Su, et al.[26]). Furthermore, integrating strain measurements into an equivalent displacement field allows the incorporation of diffraction-measured strain fields as inputs to this framework (Koko, et al.[27]). This has recently been applied to analyse HR-EBSD observations of stable mixed-mode cleavage crack propagation in single crystal silicon (Koko, et al.[28]). In situ HR-EBSD therefore has the capability to observe and quantify both the elastic and plastic conditions at the crack tip.

In this study, a short fatigue crack was initiated in a single crystal nickel foil specimen. Subsequently, the crack was loaded and observed in situ as the crack tip region was mapped by HR-EBSD. The full-field strain data was integrated into displacements and then employed as inputs to a FE post-processing framework that evaluated the local elastic strain fields in terms of mixed-mode stress intensity factors.

MATERIAL AND METHODS

Sample preparation and fatigue crack nucleation

Laser machining was used to cut specimens from a single crystal foil (surface normal near [001]) composed of a Ni alloy. The specimen's shape and dimensions are shown in FIGURE 1. Specimens were first electro-polished to create a surface suitable to high-quality pattern acquisition during HR-EBSD, and then subjected to high-frequency fatigue testing to nucleate a crack. Each specimen was attached to a high-power ultrasonic generator, capable of producing mechanical vibrations at a 20 kHz frequency. The outer ring aligns with the holder, while the hammerhead serves to augment its inertia: the hammerhead lags behind as the bulk specimen moves in response to the ultrasonic displacement. This results in cyclic bending of the 'neck' region to achieve high frequency tension/compression ($R=-1$), with the maximum stress at the specimen surface (Gong[29], Gong and Wilkinson[30]). A non-contact laser-based method, complemented by automated analysis tools, stopped the fatigue test when crack nucleation was detected (typically within a few seconds to minutes).

FIGURE 1 The geometry of the specimen.

In-situ tensile testing in SEM

A test specimen with a suitable fatigue crack (length $\sim 230 \mu\text{m}$) was selected and then mounted onto a 2 kN Deben® 70° pre-tilted loading stage inside a Carl Zeiss Merlin field emission gun scanning electron microscope (FEG-SEM). A jig was designed to hold and apply a tensile force to the specimen via two pins in contact with the hammerhead, as shown in FIGURE 2. In both fatigue loading and tensile loading, the maximum force was aligned parallel to near [100], i.e. along the 'neck' of the Ni-foil specimen. Prior to testing, six cycles of plasma cleaning and purging were carried out for the SEM chamber and the loading stage with mounted specimen, with each cycle lasting approximately an hour.

FIGURE 2 SEM image of the specimen prepared to tensile loading. The arrow highlights the position of the fatigue crack.

The loading procedure comprised four steps in addition to an initial observation (step 0) that established an unloaded reference. Force control was used, with a maximum jaw travel speed of 0.1 mm/min. The load was incremented in steps of 0.25 N, each followed by a 5-minute load-holding phase to stabilise. Electron backscatter patterns (EBSPs) were collected using a Bruker eFlash CCD camera to map the crack tip region. Using conditions of 20 kV/2 nA beam, 20 mm working distance and 300 ms exposure time per pattern (800×600 pixel detector), scans of 193×144 steps were conducted with step size of 0.1 μm , resulting in an approximate mapping area of 20 μm ×15 μm .

High resolution strain mapping and FE post-processing

The calculation of the elastic strain field involved an iterative cross-correlation process between the EBSPs and a reference pattern (EBSP₀) obtained at step 0 that was assumed to be stress free (Koko, et al.[31]). *AstroEBSD* (Britton, et al.[32]), a pattern indexing algorithm based upon an astronomical approach, was incorporated in the analysis to improve accuracy. The deformation gradient tensor was calculated using measurements of the crystal interplanar spacing and zone axes. With an additional assumption of no traction perpendicular to the surface and an elastic material model showing single crystal anisotropy, the elastic strain tensor at every point in the scanning area was obtained. For details of the calculation, the reader is referred to [19], Britton and Wilkinson[33], Britton, et al.[34], Wilkinson and Britton[35].

Within the context of finite elements (FE), the discretised nodal representation of the strain field can be integrated to obtain the corresponding discretised nodal representation of the displacement field ([22], Barhli, et al.[36], [Koko, et al.[37]). The rectangular grid of displacement data then served as the input boundary conditions in the FE-based post-processing analysis. A grid of the same size and spacing was created (i.e. 1 data point per node). Under the assumption of linear anisotropic elasticity, the finite element analysis was conducted using CPS4 elements. Direct evaluation of the *J*-integral was achieved using the inbuilt algorithms (virtual crack extension) in the ABAQUS software (version 6.14). The change in the *J*-integral between load steps was used to evaluate the changes in the mixed-mode stress intensity factors (SIFS) using a mode-decomposition method, which applies an auxiliary field to decompose the constituent field elements (Molteno and Becker[38]).

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

To obtain an estimate of the expected *J*-integral values, a finite element model of a section of the test specimen was created in ABAQUS with a crack in the same location and of the same length and orientation. A tensile load of 1.00 N was applied to the hammerhead to represent the remote boundary condition ('Remote BC') in accordance with the experimental design. Linear elastic material properties were specified with orientations defined according to EBSD data (orthotropic, $D_{1111}=D_{2222}=D_{3333}=251.3$, $D_{1122}=D_{1133}=D_{2233}=160.9$, $D_{1212}=D_{1313}=D_{2323}=129.4$ GPa), and the component was meshed with local adjustments to accommodate the shape of the (111) crack, as illustrated in FIGURE 3A. The simulation was executed using C3D20 elements. FIGURE 3B and 3C show the displacement fields obtained by this simulation. The calculated SIFs are summarised in TABLE 1 and FIGURE 7, and increase linearly with load.

FIGURE 3 Finite element model with a tensile load of 1.00 N applied to the hammerhead as Remote BC: (A) Mesh (B) Displacement U1 (C) Displacement U2.

The strain tensor fields calculated through the HR-EBSD method are shown in FIGURE 4 for each load step. There is an overall increasing trend of the magnitude of the strain fields as the applied load increases and localised strain concentrations occur in the vicinity of the crack. The rectangular area in some of the strain plots is the outcome of beam damage on the specimen surface, which was evident in the HR-EBSD ‘quality’ plots. Such damage has significant effect in ε_{xz} and ε_{yz} , but has a negligible effect in the 2D analysis that was used to extract the mode I and mode II stress intensity factors.

To simplify the FE post-processing, the strain field data were cropped and rotated to orient the crack horizontally. The energy integral calculation was performed within a selected area that conformed to the boundaries of the available data. The contour definitions are illustrated in FIGURE 5, where the contour is centred at the crack tip and contour number increases with each additional layer of the elements contained within it. (i.e., contour 1 contains the element layer surrounding the immediate crack tip, contour 2 includes an additional layer outside of that, and so on). The crack tip was identified by examination of the discontinuity and gradients in both the strain field and the geometrically necessary dislocation (GND) density field.

The J -integral and both the mode I (K_I) and mode II (K_{II}) SIFs that were obtained through direct evaluation of the local HR-EBSD-derived strain fields are presented in FIGURE 6. Each plot represents one load step from 0.25 N to 1 N, relative to the unloaded step, and shows the values obtained for the calculations with contours 1-15 up to a maximum contour length of 12 μm . In the initial load steps (steps 1 and 2, corresponding to 0.25 N and 0.50 N), the variations in the SIFs and J values for the different contours are minimal. In the subsequent steps, the fluctuations become more significant, but there is a significant degree of consistency and the results are effectively path insensitive as the contours expand from the crack tip.

Outliers, defined as data points exceeding three standard deviations from the mean, were removed from each set of 15 results. This filter effectively excludes the data points close to the crack tip. The mean and standard error were calculated using the remaining data, to represent the J -integral and SIFs at each load step. These values are detailed in TABLE 1. These HR-EBSD data are compared in the table with the values predicted by the finite element model with remote boundary conditions (‘Remote BC’). FIGURE 7 visualises the trends in these values as the load was increased.

FIGURE 4 Elastic strain tensor maps measured at (A) 0.25 N, (B) 0.50 N, (C) 0.75 N, (D) 1.00 N.

FIGURE 5 Contour definition in cropped and rotated area for J -integral analysis.

FIGURE 6 J -integral and stress intensity factors evaluated from the HR-EBSD obtained fields.

TABLE 1 J-integral and stress intensity factors with HR-EBSD (local) and remote boundary conditions (BC). For the remote BC elastic model, the ratio of K_I/K_{II} is constant with load at 1.91.

Load (N)	J-integral HR-EBSD ($J\cdot m^{-2}$)	J-integral (remote BC) ($J\cdot m^{-2}$)	K_I HR-EBSD ($MPa\cdot m^{0.5}$)	K_I (remote BC) ($MPa\cdot m^{0.5}$)	K_{II} HR-EBSD ($MPa\cdot m^{0.5}$)	K_{II} (remote BC) ($MPa\cdot m^{0.5}$)	K_I/K_{II} HR-EBSD
0.25	0.58±0.023	0.82	0.22 ± 0.003	0.18	0.07±0.003	0.09	3.14
0.50	3.91±0.034	1.64	0.64 ± 0.005	0.35	0.21±0.010	0.18	3.05
0.75	6.25±0.170	2.45	0.95 ± 0.003	0.53	0.14±0.018	0.28	6.78
1.00	10.64±0.098	3.27	1.51 ± 0.013	0.71	0.28±0.031	0.37	5.39

FIGURE 7 Comparison of stress intensity factors obtained with local measurements (HR-EBSD) and remote boundary conditions (Remote BC).

FIGURE 7 shows that both the local values of the mode I SIF, K_I , obtained by analysis of the local strains by HR-EBSD and those predicted for remote boundary conditions increase with applied load. The discrepancy between them is judged to arise from bending of the specimen due to misalignment in the loading jig, which could significantly increase the surface stresses above those predicted for pure tension. This result demonstrates that the HR-EBSD method provides a reasonable measurement of the local elastic strain field that acts on the crack tip.

The HR-EBSD assessment also quantifies the local mode II elastic strain field surrounding the crack tip region. Interestingly, unlike K_I , the value of K_{II} does not increase monotonically with load and saturates at around $0.2 MPa\cdot m^{0.5}$. This significantly increases K_I/K_{II} above the constant value of 1.91 predicted with the elastic model for remote loading (see TABLE 1). This shows that the actual mode II elastic field at the crack tip is limited in magnitude, which may be explained by stress

relaxation from localised plastic deformation. The local observation therefore quantifies the critical stress field for slip activation at the crack tip on crystallographic planes parallel to the stage I fatigue crack plane. This mode of plastic deformation is fundamental to the mechanism of fatigue crack propagation (Zhang, et al.[39], Karamitros, et al.[40]), and its critical value has been evaluated, in situ, for the first time.

CONCLUSIONS

In situ observation and evaluation of the elastic strain field acting on a short fatigue crack tip has been achieved for the first time. The full-field strain tensor map was retrieved by electron backscatter pattern correlation (HR-EBSD), and a parameterisation of the surface strains in terms of stress intensity factors was done by integration in finite element post-processing framework. The Mode I stress intensity factor showed a linear increase with load, whereas the local mode II stress intensity factor saturated. The saturation is attributed to slip activation at the crack tip at a critical state of shearing.

Future studies will obtain full-field local measurements of the total strain field by digital image correlation and also a quantitative analysis of the dislocation distribution and character by HR-EBSD. Such measurements in combination have the capability to offer a comprehensive depiction of both the elastic and plastic deformations occurring at the crack tip that govern the fatigue crack growth rate. In the longer term, interactions of short fatigue cracks with grain boundaries and the influence of load history, such as overloads, may be studied by this method.

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